

Ayurvedic Medical Destination - Selection Criterion (Preference of Coimbatore City)

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INTRODUCTION

Indian being the land of ayurveda, is a nation with resource rich and diversity, attract tourists those who prefer to avail alternative treatment methods i.e., both foreign and domestic tourist visiting an unknown tourist destination across India for medical treatments expects their host to offer a package of services that included three R's (Relax, Recharge and Rejuvenate). Ayurvedic wellness and treatment industry in India offer a basket of services to their guest realising this mind set, these days offer package of alternate traditional therapies like: Yoga, Meditation, Ayurveda, Naturopathy and medical food to their tourist guest that varies for a period of seven days to 41 days. Primary reasons for the growth of ayurvedic medical tourism in India, is the very effective treatments, faith of the foreigners and domestic patient on the Indian's age old techniques of treatments. Moreover, numbers of ayurvedic centers are functioning in various Indian states owned by both State Government agencies and the private entrepreneurs, which are world renowned center. These centers offer highly cost effective medical treatments says 50 to 80 per cent cheaper compared to other medical treatments offered in the developed countries like UK (United Kingdom), USA (United States of America) and in other European Countries. Affordability of medical tourism combined with the leisure travel, excitement and entertainment of natural sceneries also attract foreigner and other domestic tourist to travel across India. Moreover, the

ABSTRACT

Primary reasons for the growth of ayurvedic medical tourism in India, is the very effective treatments, faith of the foreigners and domestic patient on the Indian's age old techniques of treatments. Moreover, numbers of ayurvedic centers are functioning in various Indian states owned by both State Government agencies and the private entrepreneurs, which are world renowned center. This study aim to identify the primary reasons stated by the tourist for selection of Coimbatore for medical tourist. The study declared that Coimbatore is considered as mostly reliable ayurvedic medical tourist destination. The city also offers very cost economic medical tourism center, the doctors and therapists, who are also considered as well-trained and knowledgeable. The authors suggested the private ayurvedic medical institutions to pay more attention in promoting Coimbatore as the more reliable hub for ayurvedic treatments, rejuvenation and metal cum physical relaxation.

KEYWORDS: Ayurvedic Treatment, Medical Tourism, Coimbatore

foreign tourists are prefer to travel through the various promotional measures adopted by Indian Governments tourism promotional activities of "Incredible India" and Government of India had relaxed various norms for availing medical visa, the less waiting time for getting visa also motivates number of tourist to visit India.

Issues Focused in the Study

Number of elements and factors influences the performances of medical tourism industry in India. Right from the tourist operators, selection of travel medium, selection of travel location, nature of services to be availed and the institution that offer services, its infrastructure facilities, Government policies and rules, support service providers like: insurance companies etc., plays an important role in determining the quality of travel and medical tourism services offered in a selected destination. Mentioned parameters considered as conduct of this study.

Review of Literature

Selective reviews collected for assessing the researchable issue is presented in this section.

Padmasani and Remya (2015) claimed that healthcare industry in India is fastest growing, world class treatment facilities were highly qualified in Indian hospitals and also through medical tourism the traditionally practiced Ayurveda has got a new face-upliftment in the international

market. Sajjad (2015) found that female tourist patients exceeded the male tourist patients who travelled to India for treatment into and within India. India has off-late become an important destination for medical tourists because of high-quality medical services, low cost and ease and affordability of travel. Edwin and Nishad (2016) have commented that the integrated Ayurveda centric medical tourism promotion activities in Kerala with the support of local agencies along with public-private participation of local Government partnerships has push the growth of medical tourism sector. Thoke and Madan (2017) study confined that tourists' satisfaction with the holistic ayurvedic medical treatments such as: Ayurveda treatment, Spa, Yoga, Medication, Wellness, Unani, Sidha, Naturopathy etc., influences the tourist to recommend this treatment techniques to others and their intention to travel to the same destination in future. Medical tourist perception towards health tourism facilities and services offered in Karnataka was investigated by Kaboor and Somashekar (2018). The authors found that ayurvedic treatment quality, authentication of treatment and medicine used for treatment and the present location of treatment resorts across Karnataka attract more tourist to select this destination for both travel and medical treatment. The sample tourists were observed to be satisfied with the nature of tourism package offered and age-old treatment techniques followed by the therapist.

At the end of the reviews assessment it has been understood that Indian has massive potential for growth of medical tourism and India is considered as the major hub for alternative medical treatments. Numbers of factors are

influences the tourist travel to India. These factors greatly influence the tourist in selection of tourist destinations.

Aims of the Article

- To assess demographic status of ayurvedic medical tourist visiting Coimbatore City.
- To identified the primary reasons stated by the tourist for selection of Coimbatore for medical tourist.

Methodology of the Paper

The article is descriptive in nature. Convenient sampling survey was applied for collection of data from sample of 250 ayurvedic medical tourist who had temporarily visited Coimbatore for medical treatment.

Results and Discussion

Coimbatore is recognised as one of the prominent ayurvedic medical treatment center in Tamil Nadu. Geographic closeness of Coimbatore to Kerala, suitable climatic condition and availability of various herbs and plant vegetation has made Coimbatore a more suitable center for ayurvedic medical treatment. The Arya Vaidhya Pharmacy (AVP) and Kottakal Arya Sala are considered as the one-stop solution for the various ailments, these centers are considered to the pride of Coimbatore. These centers function in Coimbatore city since 1940. Following these two sister concerns, many ayurvedic treatment centers have migrated from Kerala to Coimbatore, as the city has more infrastructure facilities, has well qualified doctors and trained therapists. Number of foreign and domestic tourist from Maharashtra, New Delhi, Kerala, Kolkata and across Tamil Nadu frequently travel to these ayurvedic treatment for rejuvenation, relaxation and for medical treatments.

TABLE: 1 DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC OF TOURIST

Sl. No	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender			
1.	Male	88	39.11
2.	Female	137	60.89
	Total	225	100
Age			
1.	20-25years	40	17.78
2.	26- 30 years	61	27.11
3.	31-35 years	24	10.67
4.	36-45 years	20	8.89
5.	45-50 years	41	18.22
6.	Above 51 years	39	17.33
	Total	225	100
Educational Qualification			
1.	School Level	24	10.67
2.	UG Level	108	48.00
3.	PG Level	64	28.44
4.	Professionals	29	12.89
	Total	225	100
Occupation			
1.	Agriculturist	8	3.56
2.	Businessman	27	12.00
3.	Professional	109	48.44
4.	Home Maker	57	25.33
5.	Retired Person	24	10.67
	Total	225	100
Nativity			
1.	Indian	175	77.78
2.	Foreign	25	11.11
3.	NRI	25	11.11
	Total	225	100

Source: Primary Data

Demographic assessment of the tourist revealed that that 60.89 per cent of the ayurvedic medical tourists are female as surveyed and 39.11 per cent of the samples are found to be male. It was observed that sample populations are aged between 26- 30 years (27.11 per cent) and 48 per cent of the ayurvedic medical tourist are graduates, 28.44 per cent of the sample subjects have completed post-graduation. Similarly, 12.89 per cent of the tourists are observed to be professionals. Over, 77.78 per cent of the medical tourists are Indians and equal portion of 11.11 per cent are observed to foreign tourist and NRIs (Non-Resident Indians).

TABLE: 2 PRIMARY REASON FOR SELECTING A SPECIFIC AYURVEDIC CENTER IN COIMBATORE

Reasons	Sum	Mean	Rank
Reliable Destination	920	4.08	1
Excellent Medical Treatment Low Cost	804	3.58	6
Easy Accessibility	796	3.52	10
Picturesque Locations	775	3.45	14
Combination of Medical & Package	789	3.51	11
Best Alternative Medicines (Ayurveda)	787	3.50	12
Combination of Therapies	820	3.65	4
Knowledge of Valuable Herbs	786	3.49	13
Well-Trained & Knowledgeable Doctors	797	3.54	9
No Side Effects	753	3.34	15
Pavement Relief to Aliments	806	3.58	6
Peaceful Environment	799	3.56	8
Reputation of Medical Centers / Hospitals	822	3.65	4
Age Old Treatment Practices	832	3.70	3
Good Administrative Procedures followed in Hospitals / Medical Centers	854	3.79	2

Source: Primary Data

Reasons stated by the sample medical tourist for selection of Coimbatore as their tourist destination are ranked in the place of one to fourteen. The ranked variables are listed as: reliable destination (81.60 per cent/ mean 4.08), good administrative procedures followed in hospitals/ medical centers (75.80 per cent/ mean 3.79), age old treatment practices (74 per cent/ mean 3.70), combination of therapies and reputation of medical centers/hospitals (73 per cent/ mean 3.65), excellent medical treatment low cost and pavement relief to aliments (71.60 per cent/ mean 3.58), peaceful environment (71.20 per cent/ mean 3.56), well trained and knowledge doctors (70.80 per cent/ mean 3.54), easy accessibility (70.40 per cent/ mean 3.52), combination of medical and package (70.20 per cent/ mean 3.51), best alternative ayurvedic medicines (70 per cent/mean 3.50), knowledge of valuable herbs (69.80 per cent/ mean 3.49), picturesque locations (69 per cent/ mean 3.45) and no side effects in the ayurvedic treatment (66.80 per cent/ mean 3.34).

TABLE: 3 COMBINED RESULTS OF ROTATED FACTOR ANALYSIS PRIMARY REASON FOR SELECTING A SPECIFIC AYURVEDIC CENTER IN COIMBATORE

Variables	Reasons for Selecting a Specific Ayurvedic Center				
	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low
X ₁ -Reliable Destination	.571	-	.522	-	-
X ₂ -Excellent medical treatment low cost	-	.740	-	-	-
X ₃ -Easy Accessibility	-	.590	-	-	-
X ₄ -Picturesque locations	-	-	-	-	.866
X ₅ -Combination of medical & package	-	-	-	-	.621
X ₆ -Best Alternative Medicines (Ayurveda)	-	.664	-	-	-
X ₇ -Combination of Therapies	-	-	-	-	-
X ₈ -Knowledge of valuable herbs	-	-	-	.673	-
X ₉ -Well-trained & Knowledgeable Doctors	.643	-	-	-	-
X ₁₀ -No side Effects	.906	-	-	-	-
X ₁₁ -Pavement relief to aliments	-	-	.851	-	-
X ₁₂ -Peaceful Environment	-	-	-	.805	-
X ₁₃ -Reputation of medical centers / Hospitals	-	-	.683	-	-
X ₁₄ -Age old treatment practices	.764	-	-	-	-
X ₁₅ -Good administrative procedures followed in Hospitals / medical centers	-	.837	-	-	-
Eigen value	3.69	2.20	1.89	1.47	1.40
% of Variance	34.58	24.63	12.61	9.77	6.32
Cumulative	34.58	59.21	71.82	81.59	87.91
Reliability Analysis Result -Cronbach's Alpha					

Sample Data Validation

KMO's Measure of Sampling Adequacy .896
 Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square 173.6
 DF 16
 Sig .105
 Sig .000
 Level of Significance: 5 per cent

Elaborate data analysis reveals that reasons for selecting a specific ayurvedic center. First factor like: reliable destination, well-trained & knowledgeable doctors, no side effects and age old treatment practices. Second factor like: excellent medical treatment low cost, easy accessibility, best alternative medicines (Ayurveda) and good administrative procedures followed in hospitals / medical centers. Third factor like: reliable destination, pavement relief to ailments and reputation of medical centers / hospitals. Fourth factor like: knowledge of valuable herbs and peaceful environment. Fifth factor like: picturesque locations and combination of medical & package.

Finding and Conclusion

Medical tourism is an emerging trend in the tourism industry with the privatisation of health care services. Especially medical tourism is gaining importance in developing countries like India. The study declared that Coimbatore is considered as mostly reliable ayurvedic medical tourist destination. The city also offers very cost economic medical tourism center, the doctors and therapists, who are also considered as well-trained and knowledgeable. The authors suggested the private ayurvedic medical institutions to pay more attention in promoting Coimbatore as the more reliable hub for ayurvedic treatments, rejuvenation and metal cum physical relaxation.

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